

Research Paper

Evaluating the behaviour of a composite of CaCl₂ and vermiculite for thermochemical adsorption energy storage: Experimental tests during the charging and discharging phases

Laura Vallese^{a,b,*}, Giulia Lombardo^{a,b}, Davide Menegazzo^{a,b}, Sara Bordignon^b, Michele De Carli^b, Simona Barison^c, Filippo Agresti^c, Eleonora Baccega^d, Sergio Bobbo^a, Laura Fedele^a, Michele Bottarelli^d

^a Construction Technologies Institute, National Research Council (CNR), Corso Stati Uniti 4, 35127 Padova, Italy

^b Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Padova, Via Venezia 1, 35131 Padova, Italy

^c Institute of Condensed Matter Chemistry and Energy Technologies, National Research Council (CNR), Corso Stati Uniti 4, 35127 Padova, Italy

^d Department of Architecture, University of Ferrara, Via Quartieri 8, 44121 Ferrara, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Thermal energy storage
Thermochemical material
Salt hydrate

ABSTRACT

Thermal energy storage plays a pivotal role in reducing the gap between energy supply and demand, as well as facilitating the integration of renewable energy sources. Thermochemical adsorption energy storage has the advantage of higher energy density compared to sensible and latent heat systems. For the application in buildings, salt hydrates combined in composite materials are among the most suitable thermochemical mediums, since they charge (dehydrate) at low temperatures.

In this work, the charging and discharging behaviour of a thermochemical composite material consisting of vermiculite and CaCl₂ was assessed through experimental tests, performed with samples of different sizes. With the aim of aiding the design of an innovative thermal energy storage prototype in the context of the European project ECHO, this research investigated correspondence between the different experimental tests and signs of degradation of the selected material.

First, the material was synthesized, and a thermogravimetric analysis was conducted to estimate the temperatures and absolute humidities characterising the onset of the different hydration and dehydration steps of CaCl₂. Then, a thermobalance was employed to perform consecutive dehydration tests. Finally, ten cycles including discharging and charging phases were investigated using a small lab-scale setup, consisting of an open circuit with recirculation. Results agreed that temperatures higher than 100 °C are required to reach the anhydrous state at an absolute humidity equal to 7.3 g/kg of dry air.

Moreover, degradation of the material was assessed in the last four cycles, showing that the adsorption rate decreases by 20 %. This degradation can be attributed to the lowered porosity of the material in the last cycles, which might have slowed down the air passing through the material bed.

The findings of this research provide relevant insights into the behavior of the vermiculite-CaCl₂ composite as a candidate for thermochemical adsorption energy storage, thus contributing to the development and spread of these systems.

1. Introduction

The reduction of the greenhouse gases emissions is crucial in the fight against climate change. The European Green Deal has set ambitious targets, aiming for a 55 % reduction in emissions by 2030 compared to 1990 levels, and to achieve net zero emissions by 2050 [1]. In Europe,

37 % of the final energy consumption is attributable to the residential, commercial, and public sectors [2]. Since a significant portion of this energy is used for heating and cooling buildings, thermal energy storage (TES) emerges as a key technology to meet the decarbonization goals. TES enables the efficient conversion and storage of energy in thermal form, allowing the reduction of the gap between energy supply and demand [3]. Additionally, TES facilitates the integration of renewable

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: laura.vallese@phd.unipd.it (L. Vallese).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2024.125311>

Received 30 August 2024; Received in revised form 2 December 2024; Accepted 22 December 2024

Available online 24 December 2024

1359-4311/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Nomenclature

DSC	Differential Scanning Calorimetry
HP	Heat Pump
MM	Molecular Mass
RH	Relative Humidity
SIM	Salt In Matrix
TCM	Thermochemical Material
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
TGA	Thermogravimetric Analysis

energy sources, addressing the issue of their intermittency and enhancing energy efficiency in buildings thanks to load shifting. Reduction of emissions is also possible thanks to the minimization of starts and stops in systems based on boilers [4].

TES is generally classified in three categories, depending on the working principle. Sensible heat storage stores and releases thermal energy by increasing or decreasing the temperature of the storage medium, typically water, whose energy storage density reaches values of 0.2 GJ/m³. Latent heat storage, on the other hand, takes advantage of phase change materials to store or release energy during melting or crystallisation at almost constant temperature, achieving storage density varying between 0.3 and 0.5 GJ/m³. Compared to these two technologies, thermochemical storage is characterised by the highest energy storage density, in the range of 0.5–3 GJ/m³ [5]. During charging, an endothermic reaction dissociates the chemical bonds of a thermochemical material (TCM). The resulting components can be maintained apart, storing energy, for a certain time. When discharge is required, heat is released through a reversible exothermic reaction, which forms again the original chemical bonds. The choice of a suitable TCM depends on the selection criteria and on the application. Salt hydrates are among the most suitable TCMs for low temperature applications, thanks to their high energy densities and low temperatures required for dehydration. Including them in composite materials helps counteract their corrosiveness and their tendency to agglomerate, which hinders reversibility, as well as heat and mass transfer [6].

In the framework of ECHO (“Efficient Compact Modular Thermal Energy Storage System”, project number 101096368), a hybrid TES system is under development [7]. The project aims to design and demonstrate a plug-and-play, flexible and digitally controlled system consisting of both thermochemical adsorption and phase change technologies. The system integrates a heat pump (HP) which converts excess electricity into heat, thus allowing load shifting. The heat provided by the HP at 80 °C is used to charge a composite TCM, consisting of vermiculite and CaCl₂. The composite has been chosen after having carried out different studies in the context of the project [8,9,10]. Calcium chloride hexahydrate (CaCl₂·6H₂O) stands out among salt hydrates for its high chemical stability and low corrosiveness, as well as its availability and low cost [9]. Its dehydration (charging) and hydration (discharging) reactions are described by Eq. (1):

This reaction proceeds through multiple steps: during hydration, first CaCl₂ gains one molecule (0–1), then it transitions from one to two (1–2), from two to four (2–4), and finally to six adsorbed molecules (4–6) [10]. Table 1 summarizes the theoretical mass increase of CaCl₂ during each hydration/dehydration step, accounting for the molecular masses (MMs) of CaCl₂ and H₂O.

For synthesizing composite TCMs, host matrixes are chosen among adsorbents or materials with high porosity and thermal conductivity [11]. Vermiculite was selected as host matrix because it is a natural inert mineral, whose advantages include a large pore structure, lightweight,

Table 1

Theoretical mass increase of CaCl₂ during the different hydration/dehydration steps.

Nr. of adsorbed H ₂ O molecules	MM [g/mol]	Mass increase (water gain) [%]
0	111	0
1	129	16
2	147	32
4	183	65
6	219	97

low cost and durability [6,8]. Its macropores ensure protection against corrosion and can improve both the salt impregnation and the kinetics of moisture migration. Composites of this matrix with CaCl₂ have demonstrated optimal water uptake capacity and energy storage density, especially in open systems [9]. They have already been investigated in lab-scale prototypes, showing optimal thermal performance compared to other candidates [6]. Aydin et al. [12] chose this composite material to develop an open-sorption pipe, showing good cyclability and durability and an energy density of 290 kWh/m³. This value was confirmed by Casey et al. [13], who evaluated the thermal performance of three TCMs. The composite of vermiculite and CaCl₂ had the best thermal and cyclic performance. Aydin et al. [14] numerically and experimentally studied a sorption storage system driven by a HP. The composite of vermiculite and CaCl₂ resulted as the most promising thanks to its hygrothermal and cyclic features, exhibiting an energy density of 170 kWh/m³. Khosravi et al. [15] used the composite as desiccant material for an evaporative cooler, observing fast reaction, high equilibrium moisture content and desorption rate at 80 °C.

This study aims to evaluate the behaviour of the selected material during the charging and discharging phases by using different experimental equipment and sample sizes, focusing on its cyclability and durability. The tests included a thermogravimetric analysis of the TCM, consecutive dehydrations of the material at different temperatures in a thermobalance, and ten charging and discharging tests in an open circuit.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Synthesis of the material

The composite of CaCl₂ and vermiculite was synthesized through the vacuum impregnation method, which determines higher volumetric energy density and optimal cycling stability [10]. A saturated CaCl₂ solution was prepared and impregnated in vermiculite in a vacuum chamber. The pump was used to create vacuum three times in a row, waiting five minutes between each time. After filtering the excess solution, the final material was completely dehydrated at 160 °C in the oven, resulting in a final mass fraction of salt ranging between 70 and 80 %.

2.2. Combined TGA-DSC measurements

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) tests were performed on samples of the salt-in-matrix (SIM) of the order of 10–20 mg. The instrument in Fig. 1 was used for combined TGA-DSC (differential scanning calorimetry) measurements, which were performed in humid air at different vapour pressure values. The accuracy of the instrument is reported in Table 2. Synthetic dry air (Airlíquide) was kept in a cylinder and was humidified by flowing through a bubbler immersed in a thermostatic bath at 20 °C and vapour pressure equal to 0.023 atm. To obtain other vapor pressure values, the temperature of the thermostatic bath was changed accordingly, and the humid air was mixed with different amounts of dry air withdrawn from the cylinder. The SIM sample was first completely dehydrated at 200 °C, then hydrated by lowering the temperature until room conditions, and finally dehydrated again

Fig. 1. TA Instruments SDT-Q600 for combined TGA-DSC measurements.

Table 2
Accuracy of the considered equipment.

Measured parameter	Sensor	Accuracy
Temperature [°C]	T-type thermocouple	± 0.5 K
	NTC type N	−20 to 0 °C ± 0.4 K, 0 to + 70 °C ± 0.2 K, +70 to + 100 °C ± 0.6 K
Relative humidity (RH) [%]	Capacitive	± 2 % RH in the range < 90 % RH at nominal temperature (25 ± 3 °C)
Mass [g]	Thermobalance KERN DLB 160-3A	± 0.003 g (linearity)
Calorimetric accuracy	Combined TGA-DSC	± 2 % (based on metal standards)
Mass [g]	Weighing scale KERN FES 33 K-4	± 0.3 g (linearity)

increasing the temperature up to 111 °C.

The visible onsets of each hydration and dehydration step were included in the Van't Hoff equation (Eq. (2)) to obtain the enthalpy and entropy variations, allowing then to extrapolate the onsets at various temperature and pressure values through linear fits.

$$\ln\left(\frac{p_{eq}}{p_0}\right) = -\frac{\Delta H}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S}{R} \quad (2)$$

where p_{eq} is the equilibrium pressure, p_0 is the standard pressure (1 atm), ΔH is the enthalpy variation, ΔS is the entropy variation, R is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature.

2.3. Charging tests in a thermobalance

The first series of data regarding the charging phase was collected with the precision thermobalance KERN DLB 160-3A (Fig. 2), using a sample of 7 g of SIM. The accuracy of the instrument is reported in Table 2. Firstly, the hydration of the sample was performed at room temperature, with the aid of a fan and monitoring its weight gain through a scale. The SIM was then charged in the thermobalance through consecutive temperature steps, from 40 °C to 100 °C, at a rate of 1 mg every 30 s. A second test was performed with a new fully hydrated sample, that was then dehydrated at 85 °C and 95 °C, at the same rate. The sample in the hydrated and dehydrated state is depicted in Fig. 3. All the tests with the thermobalance can be assumed to have taken place in a constant absolute humidity condition, namely 7.3 g/kg of dry air, which was the room condition during the measurements.

2.4. Cyclability tests in an open circuit

Hydration and dehydration tests of the SIM were carried out in an open circuit with recirculation, consisting of stainless-steel tubes

Fig. 2. Thermobalance (KERN) with the hydrated SIM sample.

(diameter of 100 mm) and including an electric heater and a 24 V fan (Fig. 4-a). On the left-hand side, the circuit included a hole with a diameter of 10 mm, used to withdraw room air. Before starting the cycles, the fabricated composite TCM was completely dehydrated in the oven at 160 °C. 130 g of SIM were placed in a section of the vertical tube in the left-hand side, forming a 50 mm thick bed. The entire setup was positioned on the weighing scale KERN FES 33 K-4 (measuring range between 0.1 g and 33000 g), to monitor the amount of water adsorbed or released by the SIM bed. Both the charging and discharging phases were performed by letting room air enter from the hole on the left and flow through the circuit. During both phases, the two ends at the top and right were partially opened through gate valves, to help the discharge of excess moisture. The heater was used only for the charging phase, regulating its power in the range of 215–220 W to reach a constant dehydrating air temperature around 80 °C at the inlet of the SIM.

The fan was maintained at the maximum voltage (24 V) for all the consecutive tests, except for the first cycle, when the fan worked at lower voltage (7 and 13 V). Increasing the air speed was necessary to avoid the blockage of the fan during the charging phase, due to the increased temperature.

The water gain or release was monitored at a timestep of 10 s and compared to Table 1 to estimate the state in which the salt hydrate was at each moment. Accordingly, each discharging phase of the material was always stopped before reaching the fully hydrated state to avoid deliquescence problems, taking 4 molecules of water as reference. On the other hand, the charging phases were stopped when the difference in water release was not visible anymore. Following this criterion, the hydrating and dehydrating phases were not the same for the different cycles (see Table 3).

The employed sensors included six T-type thermocouples and two combined sensors for temperature (negative temperature coefficient sensor – NTC) and relative humidity (capacitive sensor). They measured the temperature of the bed in the middle and 20 mm from the edge, and the temperature of the air at the inlet and outlet of the SIM, at different distances. They also measured the air relative humidity at the inlet and outlet of the bed (Fig. 4-b). All the sensors acquired data every 10 s.

The accuracy of the sensors, the thermobalance, the TGA-DSC instrument and the weighing scale are reported in Table 2.

Measurements of air flow rate or velocity were not possible in this set-up. However, an estimation can be made by considering the measured parameters. Knowing the average water gain per hour \dot{m}_w (9 g/h) and the difference of air absolute humidity Δx (around 1–1.5 g/kg of dry air) before and after entering the TCM bed, the dry air mass flow rate \dot{m}_{da} is found through Eq. (3).

Fig. 3. TCM sample in the hydrated (left) and dehydrated state (right).

a

b

Fig. 4. Experimental setup for charging and discharging of the SIM (a) and positioning of the sensors (b). The green arrow indicates the air flow direction.

Table 3
Summary of the discharging-charging cycles performed in the circuit.

Cycle	Hydration duration [h]	Dehydration duration [h]	Reached states [n° H ₂ O molecules]
1	21.33	8.67	0-4-2
2	4	8	2-4-2
3	3.65	9.72	2-4-2
4	4.22	4.9	2-4-2
5	3.73	7.27	2-4-2
6	2.68	12.1	2-3-1
7	7.37	5.38	1-5-2
8	8	7.57	2-5-2
9	4.9	7.5	2-4-2
10	6.37	7.83	2-5-2

$$\dot{m}_{da} = \frac{\dot{m}_w}{\Delta x} \quad (3)$$

The volume flow rate can be calculated by assuming an air specific volume v equal to $0.88 \text{ m}^3/\text{kg}$ of dry air (Eq. (4)), and the air velocity is obtained through Eq. (5), knowing the area A of the stainless-steel tubes.

$$\dot{V} = \dot{m}_{da} v \quad (4)$$

$$w = \frac{\dot{V}}{A} \quad (5)$$

An air velocity equal to around 2 m/s is estimated, a significantly higher value with respect to the experimental studies found in literature.

3. Results

3.1. Extrapolation of the kinetic onset curves

The TGA-DSC measurements at the highest vapour pressure, 0.018 atm , showed three hydration steps: 0–0.25, 0.25–2, 2–4–6 water

molecules. Each step is distinguished from the others by specific enthalpy and entropy variations, and equilibrium pressure. Given a certain temperature, a new step does not initiate until the related equilibrium pressure is reached. During the TGA-DSC tests, the heating/cooling rate was chosen so that the different steps could be characterised separately. At a higher rate, the steps would succeed one another very fast, and it could not be possible to distinguish them. The transition between two stages was observed from the outcome of the TGA measurements, specifically the diagram reporting the mass gain/loss in

terms of water molecules as a function of temperature, which shows plateaus in correspondence to each stage. The transition between 4 and 6 molecules was not observed, occurring instead in only one step starting from two water molecules. On the other hand, three different steps were observed during the dehydration process, namely 6-4, 4-1 and 1-0. Since the 6-4 step was very fast, it was not possible to extrapolate the onsets. Fig. 5 shows the curves extrapolated from the kinetic onsets obtained during the TGA measurements at 4 different vapour pressure values. These curves are dashed and represent the

Fig. 5. Psychrometric-like diagrams showing the areas related to each hydration (top) and dehydration (bottom) state of the TCM.

threshold to cross to reach a new hydration or dehydration step, while the TGA measurement points are marked as rounds. For both processes, the transition between 4 and 6 molecules is represented by the theoretical equilibrium curve (solid line), referred to thermodynamic literature data [16]. The span of the dashed arrows represents the temperature range explored during the TGA experiment performed at that specific absolute humidity, correspondent to a certain vapour pressure. The obtained psychrometric-like diagrams are a useful tool to get an indication of the onset temperatures required at different absolute humidities. They have been used in the following for better describing some of the data gathered during the laboratory experimentation.

3.2. Analysis of the discharging process

An overview of the two tests with the thermobalance is shown in Fig. 6, where the red dots are related to the first measurement, while the green ones to the second. The thresholds (horizontal solid lines) delimiting the different steps refer to the theoretical mass increase of CaCl_2 during hydration, based on the molecular masses of CaCl_2 and H_2O (Table 1). The points at 24 °C represent the initial state of the partially or totally hydrated SIM sample, while the others show the final state reached by the SIM at each considered dehydration temperature.

According to the results, at an absolute humidity of 7.3 g/kg of dry air, the monohydrate state is surely reached at temperatures higher or equal to 90 °C, when according to the H_2O - CaCl_2 ratio the last molecule starts to be desorbed. Working at temperatures of 80–85 °C means being close to reaching the monohydrate state. Only the dehydration of the sample at 160 °C in the oven, shown as comparison (blue dot), allowed to reach the anhydrous state.

Since in the ECHO project the HP is going to supply a maximum temperature of 80 °C, it will be necessary to work at a lower absolute humidity and possibly to integrate an electric heater to eventually increase the charging temperature of the TCM reactor, thus allowing it to completely charge.

The measurement points obtained during the charging phases with the thermobalance are then reported in the diagram of Fig. 5, to evaluate

the correspondence with the TGA tests (Fig. 7). The points at 40 and 60 °C lay in the area between the 6–4 and 4–1 onsets, showing accordance with the ratio H_2O - CaCl_2 achieved in the thermobalance, which indicate that the material is hydrated with 3–4 molecules. The points at temperatures higher than 90 °C are found in proximity of and beyond the point where the onset 4–1 is located, suggesting that the monohydrate state can be reached by charging at those temperatures, in agreement with the tests in the thermobalance. However, it should be noted that both these points and the ones at 80–85 °C appear shifted to the left of about 10 K with respect to the theoretical thresholds considered in Fig. 6. Indeed, these points would be expected to be closer to the dashed curve 1–0, which delimits on the left the area where the SIM is hydrated with one water molecule, and on the right the area where the SIM is completely dehydrated. This shift might be due to the different weight of TCM employed in the two measurements, since the material is not homogeneous. In all cases, it is evident that temperatures higher than 100 °C are required to lose the last water molecule at the considered room conditions, necessary to fully charge the TCM.

Table 3 shows an overview of the ten cycles performed in the circuit. As reported in Section 2.4, the first cycle was operated at a lower air velocity compared to the other 9 cycles, thus requiring a higher duration of the hydration phase. In general, for each cycle the hydration phase was stopped after the material had theoretically adsorbed 4 water molecules, while the charging phase ended once the scale stopped detecting the mass decrease, i.e. when the difference in weight was lower than 0.2 g for more than 30 min. The hydration phase was blocked before reaching the full hydrated state (adsorption of 6 water molecules) to avoid deliquescence issues. The water gain or release was monitored by continuously checking the increase or decrease in weight of the sample, as shown by the weighing scale display.

Data related to six charging phases in the circuit is reported in Fig. 8. For all the processes, the transition phase occurring between the switch-on of the heater and the achievement of the target charging temperature (around 80 °C) is well visible. The SIM started dehydrating already at lower temperatures, particularly at 45 °C when the outlet air absolute humidity started increasing significantly. This parameter started

Fig. 6. Final states reached for each charging test using the thermobalance. The theoretical thresholds delimiting the different steps are represented by the blue straight lines and refer to Table 1. The red dots refer to the first test, the green ones to the second, while the blue dot refers to the dehydration of the sample in the oven.

Fig. 7. Charging tests with the thermobalance reported on the kinetic onset curves diagram.

Fig. 8. Six charging tests in the circuit (the black arrows indicate the state reached by the SIM according to Table 1).

declining at around 70 °C, then stabilizing when the target temperature was reached. This indicates that at the beginning of the process the air extracts moisture more easily and is dependent on the dehydration reaction kinetics. The plateau visible at around 20 g/kg of dry air suggests that the humid air at the outlet of the SIM was in equilibrium with the room air flow entering the circuit and with the flow exiting through the two small holes located at the top and on the right side of the circuit. Towards the end of the dehydration phase, the outlet air absolute humidity tended to bring itself back to the initial value, corresponding to

the room air conditions. Most of each charging test was operated at the target temperature, allowing to reach the state at which two or even one H₂O molecules are retained, according to Table 1. This is in agreement with the previous tests, highlighting how 80 °C are not sufficient to completely charge the SIM in these conditions.

3.3. Analysis of the durability of the material

A general overview of the cycles (discharging-charging) 2–10, which

Fig. 9. Individually normalised cycles.

were performed in the circuit with the same fan setting (24 V), is depicted in Fig. 9, taking into account the same time for discharging and charging. The diagrams are individually normalised both with respect to time and to mass gain/release. They show that the qualitative behaviour of the material in terms of mass variation is the same. In particular, the mass gain during hydration is not linear, suggesting that the material adsorbs more water at the beginning of the hydration phase. Regarding the charging phase, a change in the slope of the curve is clearly observed in all cycles, indicating a lower desorption rate in the last part of the process and confirming what is observed in Fig. 8.

These remarks are supported by the trend of the gradient of the mass with respect to time. In each hydration phase, the water gain is maximum at the beginning of the process and decreases every hour. Likewise, in each charging process the water released is maximum at the beginning and decreases with time.

Considering the cycles 2–10 together, a progressive decrease in the water gain with respect to the total hydration time was observed (Fig. 10). In particular, after ten cycles the adsorption rate decreased of about 20 %, indicating a certain degree of degradation of the material.

Another useful indicator of the durability of the SIM is the ratio between temperature differences during the discharging phase, defined

in Eq. 3.

$$R = \frac{T_{out} - T_{in}}{T_{bed} - T_{in}} \quad (3)$$

where T_{out} is the air temperature at the outlet of the SIM bed, T_{in} is the inlet air temperature, and T_{bed} is the temperature in the middle of the bed.

The average ratio increases in the last four cycles (Fig. 11). While the difference between the inlet and outlet temperature is quite constant, around 3.2 K, the difference between the temperature of the bed and the inlet air decreases up to 17 % in the last four cycles, suggesting a certain degradation of the material. Moreover, the difference between the temperature of the bed and the outlet air temperature decreases up to 79 %: this could be explained by the observable lowered porosity of the material after several cycles, which may have slowed down the air after passing through the bed, thus increasing its temperature to a value closer to the bed’s temperature. The decrease in porosity was detected by trying to move the different pieces of material. After several cycles it was difficult to detach them because they had agglomerated together.

Fig. 10. Mass gradient for each discharging process.

Fig. 11. Average and maximum values of the ratio R for each cycle.

4. Conclusions

In this work, a composite of vermiculite and CaCl_2 was synthesized and tested during the dehydration and hydration phases, using different equipment. TGA scans on a 10–20 mg sample were used to extrapolate the onset kinetic curves corresponding to the different hydration steps of CaCl_2 , giving an indication of the different temperatures and absolute humidities necessary for each phase. The charging tests with the thermobalance have been compared to the diagram obtained during the TGA test, highlighting that a temperature of 80 °C, which is going to be supplied by the HP in the ECHO project, is not sufficient for complete dehydration of the material at an absolute humidity of 7.3 g/kg of dry air. This result is confirmed also by the discharging phases of the ten cycles performed in the circuit. Therefore, the HP will work at a lower absolute humidity and an additional electric heater is foreseen to increase the temperature of the air used to charge the TCM reactor. Finally, performing ten consecutive cycles allowed to evaluate the durability of the material, which showed a decrease in the adsorption rate during hydration of about 20 % in the last cycles. A decrease in the difference between the temperatures of the SIM bed and of the outlet air was especially observed in the last four cycles, suggesting that the porosity of the material may have decreased, possibly slowing down the air passing through the bed. Future work will involve air flow rate measurements, allowing to assess the power released during the discharging phase. Only an estimation of the velocity was possible in this work, indicating this kind of setup as promising for experimentation at higher velocities compared to what is found in literature.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme within the ECHO project, under grant agreement No. 101096368.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] «communication from the commission to the european parliament, the european council, the council, the european economic and social committee and the committee of the regions, The European Green Deal», Brussels, 11/12/2019.
- [2] International Energy Agency, <https://www.iea.org/regions/europe/efficient-cy-demand>.
- [3] G. Sadeghi, Energy storage on demand: Thermal energy storage development, materials, design, and integration challenges, *Energy Storage Mater.* 46 (2022) 192–222, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2022.01.017>.
- [4] J. Heier, C. Bales, E.V. Martin, Combining thermal energy storage with buildings – a review, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 42 (2015) 1305–1325, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.11.031>.
- [5] A.H. Abedin, A critical review of thermochemical energy storage systems, *Open Renew. Energy J.* 4 (fasc.1) (2011) 42–46, <https://doi.org/10.2174/1876387101004010042>.
- [6] R.-J. Clark, A. Mehrabadi, E.M. Farid, State of the art on salt hydrate thermochemical energy storage systems for use in building applications, *J. Energy Storage.* 27 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2019.101145>.
- [7] «ECHO Project | Efficient Compact Modular Thermal Energy Storage System», ECHO Project. Consultato: 13 agosto 2024. [Online]. Disponibile su: <https://echo-euproject.eu/>.
- [8] Z. Chen, Y. Zhang, Y. Zhang, Y. Su, E.S. Riffat, A study on vermiculite-based salt mixture composite materials for low-grade thermochemical adsorption heat storage, *Energy* 278 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2023.127986>.
- [9] Y. Zhang, M. Hu, Z. Chen, Y. Su, E.S. Riffat, Performance study of a thermochemical energy storage reactor embedded with a microchannel tube heat exchanger for water heating, *J. Energy Storage.* 78 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2023.110043>.
- [10] Y. Zhang, Z. Chen, Y. Zhang, Y. Su, E.S. Riffat, Parameter control in synthesis of Vermiculite- CaCl_2 composite materials for thermochemical adsorption heat storage, *Energy* 291 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.130478>.
- [11] Q. Zhao, J. Lin, H. Huang, Q. Wu, Y. Shen, E.Y. Xiao, Optimization of thermochemical energy storage systems based on hydrated salts: a review, *Energy Build.* 244 (2021) 111035, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.111035>.
- [12] D. Aydin, S.P. Casey, X. Chen, E.S. Riffat, Novel “open-sorption pipe” reactor for solar thermal energy storage, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 121 (2016) 321–334, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2016.05.045>.
- [13] S.P. Casey, D. Aydin, J. Elvins, E.S. Riffat, Salt impregnated desiccant matrices for ‘open’ thermochemical energy conversion and storage – Improving energy density utilisation through hydrodynamic & thermodynamic reactor design, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 142 (2017) 426–440, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.03.066>.
- [14] D. Aydin, S.P. Casey, X. Chen, E.S. Riffat, Numerical and experimental analysis of a novel heat pump driven sorption storage heater, *Appl. Energy.* 211 (2018) 954–974, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.11.102>.
- [15] N. Khosravi, D. Aydin, M. Karim Nezhad, E.P.A. Dogramaci, Comparative performance analysis of direct and desiccant assisted evaporative cooling systems using novel candidate materials, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 221 (2020) 113167, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2020.113167>.
- [16] P.A.J. Donkers, L.C. Sögütöglü, H.P. Huinink, H.R. Fischer, E.O.C.G. Adan, A review of salt hydrates for seasonal heat storage in domestic applications, *Appl. Energy.* 199 (2017) 45–68, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.04.080>.